

WORKING PARTS OF GRINDING MACHINES AND THEIR INTERACTION WITH LEATHER

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the working parts of buffing machines and their interaction with leather. An assessment of the processing quality for chrome-tanned leathers shows that as the concentration of abrasive grains increases and their size decreases, the nap obtained during buffing becomes finer and slightly shorter. Experimental data indicate that the nap length increases as the hardness of the leather product's treated surface decreases. In turn, hardness depends on the moisture content of the material being processed, its drying method, the type of raw material, the tanning agent and method, the fat content within the leather, and other factors.*

Keywords. *Leather sanding (grinding), abrasive material, sanding drum, contact curve, pressure roller, kinematic chain, micro unevenness.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются рабочие органы шлифовальных машин и их взаимодействие с кожей. Оценка качества обработки хромированных кож показывает, что с увеличением соотношения абразивных зерен и уменьшением их размеров полученные при шлифовании ворсинки становятся тоньше и несколько укорачиваются. Экспериментальные данные показывают, что длина ворса увеличивается с уменьшением твердости обрабатываемой поверхности кожевенного изделия. В свою очередь, твердость зависит от влажности обрабатываемого материала, способа его сушки, вида сырья, способа дубления и дубления, содержания жира в коже и других факторов.*

Ключевые слова. Шлифовка кожи, абразивный материал, шлифовальный барабан, контактная кривая, прижимной вал, кинематическая цепь, микронеровнота.

The leather buffing operation is performed after the fleshing, shaving, setting out, and staking operations, which shape the quality of the leather.

The working part of a sanding machine is a drum covered (or wrapped) with paper or cloth, to which a crushed abrasive material is bonded. As it wears down during operation, the sanding belt does not lose its cutting (sanding) ability for a certain period. This is because as the cutting edges of the abrasive grains become dull, they simultaneously heat up and soften the binding material they are in contact with [1].

The processed leather is pressed against the grinding drum (Fig. 1) with an elastic coating, usually with a rubber coating (felt on the SHMK-2 machine, felt on the MSH-600-K machine). In machines for polishing leather along its entire width, it is pressed against the surface of the feed roller by a smooth clamping shaft or a spring-loaded plate to ensure uniform transport and prevent slippage. Rotating brushes are often installed under the feed shaft of the grinding drum, and stationary brushes are rarely used. Brushes are designed for cleaning leather dust from the surface of the semi-finished product and from the feed roller, grinding drum [2]. In addition, the brushes prevent the leather from getting tangled on the feed roller or grinding drum.

If the leather (Fig. 2) is subjected to processing at a constant speed $v_n = \omega_1(r_1 + H)$, then the grinding drum rotates at a constant speed $v_p = \omega_2 R$ where ω_1 , ω_2 , r_1 and R - angular velocities and radii of the feed shaft corresponding to the grinding drum; H - material thickness,

Fig. 1. Diagram of the working bodies of various grinding machines:

a - SHMMK-2 and MSH-600-K; b - MSH-1500 and the "Velox" machine of the "Aletti" company; c - the 633A machine of the "Turner" company; d - the 632 machine of the "Turner" company with a 631V dust removal device;

1 - grinding drum; 2 - feed shaft; 3-brush shaft; 4-semi-finished product;

5-clamping shaft; 6-conveyor; 7-clamping plate; 8-fixed brush; 9-smoothing belt; 10-tensioning shaft

Then the trajectories of the abrasive belt grains relative to the semi-finished product are expressed by the following system of equations:

$$X = R(\sin \varphi \pm \frac{v_n}{v_p} \varphi);$$

$$Y = R(1 - \cos \varphi);$$

$$Z = A \sin(\varphi i),$$

where the plus (+) sign is opposite v_p and v_n for the directions, the (-) sign is the same; φ - angle of rotation of the grinding drum; A - operation of the drum movement in the direction of the Z axis; i - transmission ratio of the kinematic chain.

The elementary length of the contact curve between the abrasive grain and the workpiece.

$$dL = \sqrt{(dX)^2 + (dY)^2 + (dZ)^2} = R \sqrt{1 \pm 2 \cos \varphi \frac{v_n}{v_p} + \left(\frac{v_n}{v_p}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{Ai}{R}\right)^2 \cos^2(\varphi i)} d\varphi.$$

Since

the value of the angle that determines the full length of the contact curve is small and $i < 1$, the following can be assumed:

The corresponding length of the contact curve in the absence of oscillation

$$L' = \left(1 \pm \frac{v_p}{v_r}\right) \sqrt{\frac{2Rrh}{R+r}} \quad (2)$$

When the semi-finished product is stationary $v_p=0$, L' is equal to the contact arc.

$$L' = R\varphi_0 = \sqrt{\frac{2Rrh}{R+r}}$$

Formula (4) can be expressed as follows:

$$L = M \sqrt{\frac{2Rrh}{R+r}},$$

where the value

$$M = \sqrt{\left(1 \pm \frac{v_p}{v_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{Ai}{R}\right)^2}, \quad (3)$$

The feed of the semi-finished product and the presence of vibration of the grinding drum characterize the difference between the length of the contact curve L and the length of the contact arc L' .

Design parameters for modern grinding machines $2A=0-16$ mm; $i=4-7$; $P=125-180$ mm, in processing modes $v_p=16-29$ m/s; $v_n=0.05-0.55$ m/s. The difference between M and unity is relatively small, close to L and L' [5].

The most common types are comma-shaped and segment shaped shavings (Fig. 3). If the following conditions are met for the distances between the points of exit of adjacent abrasive grains from the material, etc., then the resulting layers will have the form of a comma:

$$S_\delta = \frac{v_n}{v_p} l < 2\overset{\cup}{CE} = 2L' \quad (4)$$

where l is the average probable distance between abrasive grains.

The average thickness of the layer removed by abrasive grains per unit of time can be determined $\delta = V/F$, where V and F are the volume of removed material and the area of the treated surface, respectively.

In equal time intervals

$$V = v_p h S \quad \text{and} \quad F = v_u M S$$

where S is the width of the processed part of the semifinished leather.

Average thickness of the removable layer

$$\delta = \frac{v_n h}{v_p M} = \frac{v_n h}{v_p \sqrt{\left(1 \pm \frac{v_n}{v_p}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{A}{Ri}\right)^2}}. \quad (5)$$

It can be seen that for a given grinding drum, at constant parameters (R, h, l), the size of the $v_n / v_p, v_p$ chips and the height of the micro platforms decrease with an increase in the ratio of S_δ micro platform heights. At the same time, with an increase in the rate of impact of abrasive particles, the wear state of the material can change from an elastic to a brittle state, which also contributes to the reduction of micro roughness [6]. However, a significant increase in the cutting speed can lead to heating of the abrasive and leather, which reduces the service life of sandpaper and deteriorates the surface quality of the processed material.

Relations (3), (4) and (5) sufficiently objectively reflect the influence of design factors and operating modes on the thickness of the resulting layer and the height of micro roughness. Experimental data show that with a decrease in the hardness of the processed surface of the leather semi-finished product, the pile length increases. In turn, hardness depends on the moisture content of the processed material, the drying method, the type of raw material, the tanning method, the fat content in the leather, and other factors.

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